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Granulomatous Hepatitis Following Intravesical Bacillus Calmette–Guérin (BCG) Therapy Presenting as Acute-on-Chronic Liver Failure (ACLF): A Case Report

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Abstract

Intravesical Bacillus Calmette–Guérin (BCG) immunotherapy is an established adjuvant treatment for non-muscle-invasive bladder carcinoma. Although generally well tolerated, systemic complications including granulomatous hepatitis are rare and potentially life-threatening. We report the case of a 74-year-old man with carcinoma urinary bladder who developed jaundice, altered sensorium, and acute kidney injury following intravesical BCG therapy. Laboratory evaluation demonstrated severe cholestatic liver injury with bilirubin 26.8 mg/dL and INR 1.9. Viral and autoimmune workup was negative. Upper gastrointestinal endoscopy revealed mild portal hypertensive gastropathy without varices. Liver biopsy demonstrated portal and lobular inflammation with epithelioid granulomas and cholestatic changes favoring BCG-related granulomatous hepatitis. This case shows a rare event, when patient developed Acute-on-Chronic Liver Failure (Granulomatous hepatitis) following BCG therapy.

Keywords: Intravesical BCG, Granulomatous hepatitis, ACLF, Acute-on-Chronic Liver Failure, cholestasis, Bladder carcinoma, transurethral resection of bladder tumor, TURBT.

Introduction:

Intravesical Bacillus Calmette–Guérin (BCG) therapy is widely used in the management of non-muscle-invasive bladder cancer following transurethral resection of bladder tumor (TURBT) [1]. While local adverse effects are common, systemic complications are uncommon and occur in less than 5% of patients [2]. Hepatic involvement due to hypersensitivity reaction or disseminated BCG infection is particularly rare [3]. Granulomatous hepatitis secondary to intravesical BCG therapy may present with fever, jaundice, cholestatic liver injury, hepatomegaly, or constitutional symptoms [4]. Because of its rarity and nonspecific presentation, diagnosis is often delayed. Histopathological examination frequently demonstrates noncaseating granulomas with variable cholestatic changes [5].

Case Presentation:

A 74-year-old man with a history of carcinoma urinary bladder, diabetes mellitus, and hypertension presented with jaundice, abdominal pain, abdominal distension, and altered sensorium. The patient had undergone transurethral resection of bladder tumor (TURBT) approximately one month prior to presentation

and subsequently received two intravesical BCG instillations over the following weeks. Approximately two weeks after the second instillation, he developed progressive jaundice with ascites followed by altered sensorium.

Laboratory investigations at admission demonstrated severe cholestatic liver dysfunction with total bilirubin of 26.8 mg/dL, INR of 1.9, serum creatinine of 2.6 mg/dL, hyponatremia (129 mEq/L), and elevated serum ammonia levels (113 micromol/L). The patient had grade III hepatic encephalopathy at presentation. Viral hepatitis markers including hepatitis A, hepatitis B, hepatitis C, hepatitis E and HIV serologies were negative. Auto-immune hepatitis workup including ANA, AMA, ASMA, and anti-LKM antibodies was negative. Ultrasound abdomen demonstrated chronic liver parenchymal disease, splenomegaly, mild ascites, and dilated portal vein suggestive of portal hypertension. Upper gastrointestinal endoscopy revealed mild portal hypertensive gastropathy without esophageal or gastric varices. He was diagnosed with ACLF (as per APASL criteria) and treated as per standard protocol of ACLF management.

The patient also had urinary tract infection due to *Klebsiella pneumoniae* with associated sepsis and acute kidney injury. Antibiotics optimized as per culture and sensitivity report. In view of persistent cholestatic liver dysfunction, and ascites, transjugular liver biopsy was performed in suspicion of rare possibility of BCG induced liver injury versus paraneoplastic manifestation of bladder carcinoma.

Histopathology Findings:

Histopathological examination showed preserved hepatic architecture with mixed portal inflammatory infiltrate composed of lymphocytes, plasma cells, neutrophils, eosinophils, and epithelioid granulomas (Figure 1A and 1B). Features of intracanalicular cholestasis was identified (Figure 1A). Mild interface hepatitis and lobular inflammation were present (Figure 2A). Mild portal fibrosis was noted (Figure 2B). Ziehl–Neelsen stain for acid-fast bacilli was negative. The histopathological impression was granulomatous hepatitis with cholestatic injury favoring BCG-related granulomatous hepatitis in the appropriate clinical setting.

Figure 1A. Liver biopsy demonstrating portal inflammatory infiltrate with epithelioid granuloma formation and cholestasis (HE stain, 40X) and Figure 1B showing Portal tract epithelioid granuloma (HE stain, 400X)

Figure 2A. Histopathological section showing Lobular inflammation (HE stain, 400X) and Figure 2B showing Portal fibrosis (Masson trichrome stain, 100X).

Discussion:

Intravesical BCG therapy is an effective immunotherapeutic modality for non-muscle-invasive bladder carcinoma [1]. Serious systemic complications are uncommon but may involve pulmonary, hepatic, vascular, osteoarticular, or disseminated manifestations [2]. Granulomatous hepatitis following intravesical BCG therapy is rare and may occur due to either disseminated

Mycobacterium bovis infection or hypersensitivity-mediated immune reaction [3]. Clinical manifestations are often nonspecific and include fever, malaise, jaundice, hepatomegaly, and abnormal liver function tests [4]. Cholestatic liver injury is the predominant biochemical pattern reported in most cases [5].

The present case is notable because the patient presented as ACLF with severe jaundice, coagulopathy, grade III hepatic encephalopathy, acute kidney injury, and portal hypertensive manifestations. Histopathology remained central to diagnosis and demonstrated noncaseating granulomas with portal and lobular inflammation. Acid-fast bacilli are frequently absent on Ziehl–Neelsen staining, as observed in our patient [6].

Differential diagnoses of granulomatous hepatitis include tuberculosis, sarcoidosis, primary biliary cholangitis, fungal infections, drug-induced liver injury, autoimmune hepatitis, and malignancy-related granulomatous reactions [7]. Comprehensive viral and autoimmune evaluation in our patient was unrevealing.

Management generally includes discontinuation of BCG therapy and initiation of anti-tubercular treatment, commonly with isoniazid, rifampicin, and ethambutol [8]. Corticosteroids may be beneficial in severe hypersensitivity-mediated disease [9]. Although the patient showed partial biochemical and clinical improvement with supportive treatment, he left against medical advice before biopsy results became available and was subsequently lost to follow-up.

Conclusion:

Granulomatous hepatitis is a rare but important complication of intravesical BCG therapy. It may present as acute-on-chronic liver failure (ACLF) with severe cholestatic liver injury and encephalopathy. A high index of suspicion, careful drug and treatment history, and liver biopsy are essential for timely diagnosis and management.

Disclosures:

Consent obtained. No conflicts of interest. No funding was received for this study.

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